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ABSTRACT

Description of the methodology used in WP4.

WP4. Grassland management

DELIVERABLE - WP4.2. Method to estimate C inputs and model SOC- sequestration measures on grasslands

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Summary

This document reports on the data collected and the methods used for Grassland Management work package (WP4) of CarboSeq. Data were long-term grassland experiments (LTE) across Europe to evaluate land use and management measures. In addition, data from the Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey (LUCAS) were used simulate plant C inputs at a greater scale across Europe. The methods used in Wp4 included specific calculations and the simulation modelling.

- These methods are not new or unique, but are commonly used. The derivation of the methods suggested by can be found in international guidelines for changes in soil carbon stocks reports such as from the IPCC (see IPCC (2006), IPCC (2019)) and the FAO on measuring and modelling (FAO, 2019).
- The methods were to evaluate and quantify changes in soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks across grassland systems in Europe in response to changes in two key drivers of ecosystem functioning: (1) land-use change and (2) management practices.
- The modelling workflow for the Rothamsted carbon model (RothC) is provided in R markdown (within an R project structure). This allows for generating input files for supplied sites, running the model, and loading in results for visualisation and analysis.
- The workflow has been tested with a) the long-term experiment (LTE) database provided by AFBI, and b) a grassland subset of the Land Use/Land Cover Area Frame Survey (LUCAS) data.

1. Introduction

Carbon sequestration in soils is a negative emission technology that can contribute to mitigate climate change. However, for European soils, a comprehensive assessment is missing on how much soil organic carbon (SOC) can be sequestered with different management options using also national data on agricultural management. The aim of CarboSeq is thus to estimate the feasible SOC-sequestration potential considering technical and socio-economic constraints. One of the key drivers for SOC-sequestration is an enhanced input of biomass to the soil.

Most SOC-models, such as RothC, struggle with to determine C inputs to soil that are important to estimate the complete realistic SOC-sequestration and GHG mitigation potential in Europe. For instance in situations where agricultural practices in the field are well-documented, C-input by aboveground and root biomass can be evaluated by reverse modelling with the RothC model. The reverse modelling then allows to determine emission factors and simple response function to extrapolate SOC change for other grassland field. One of the main tasks of WP4 was to develop (and evaluate) methodologies to use existing and new databases helping to facilitate the parametrisation of model runs with RothC and other soil SOC models for different management scenarios.

This deliverable report describes the data which were used in WP4. Data were collected from European long-term grassland experiments (LTEs) and from the Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey (LUCAS). Both datasets were used simulate plant C inputs at different scales. In addition, the LTE data were also used to calculate emission factors and the stock difference method.

For WP4 we used the Rothamsted carbon model (RothC) at on two datasets at different scales to simulate plant C inputs. The focus on plant C inputs is because it is a key factor which directly effects SOC stocks (Stewart et al., 2007). (Luo et al., 2017) reported that C inputs (including C input amount and pasture frequency system) accounted for 27% of the relative influence on rate of SOC change; while climate accounted for 25% and soil C pools and soil properties were both 24%.

Here the workflow is described and details are given on the data requirements. This includes the land management information and how the RothC simulations were run.

2. Data

In WP4 data was collected from long-term experiments (LTEs) for different purposes. We used the LTE data to calculate soil carbon stocks (Del. 4.1.) and emission factors (Del. 4.3). these same data were utilised for the simulation of plant C inputs (Del. 4.4.). Data from the Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey (LUCAS) were also used simulate plant C inputs (Del. 4.5.) at a European scale.

2.1 Input data

For RothC simulation, input data files (both with LTE and LUCAS data) were setup comprising: climate, management and site-specific parameter (clay content %) which was supplied from the WP4 database. Other parameters were entered directly into the interface were (see Fig. 1): (i) DPM/ RPM ratio = 1.44 (from manual (Coleman and Jenkinson, 2014) for grassland/cultivated crops) and (ii) sampling year sampled, here we assumed that if the actual year was not supplied the database publication date was the date the soil was sampled.

Figure 1. Structure of the pools, and flows of Carbon in the Roth-C model, including major factors controlling the fluxes (a = multiplier for effects of temperature, b = multiplier for effects of moisture, c = multiplier for effects of soil cover; DPM/RPM = Decomposable/resistant plant material ratio). Source: redrawn from Coleman and Jenkinson (1996) and Falloon and Smith (2009).

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2.2. Description of simulated LTE sites

In the original WP4 dataset there were 465 data records. This dataset was thoroughly evaluated and revised to 298 data records. Studies were removed that had: (i) a too short a timeframe (< 10 years) or (ii) measurements of soil organic C (SOC) in deeper soils (> 30 cm).

The studies were divided into two main groups. Firstly, a “Management” (where no difference in land use was reported between control and treatment plots. Studies were filtered where there was a difference or change in land-use .

2.2.1. Land Management

The land management and change group contained **212 data records** which only investigated grassland systems. Most of these studies had different management treatments and usually the experiment was designed to compare this treatment against a grassland control with no treatment. The two most common types of land management change (treatment) identified were (i) add inorganic fertilisers and (ii) add organic fertilisers (i.e. adding both N and OC) usually in the form of FYM or slurry (three studies: Hillsborough, Newcastle University and Park Grass Rothamsted (all UK)). Note, the majority of the management studies had no data on C additions and therefore it was assumed that no OC was added to the treatment plots in the subsequent RothC simulations.

2.2.2. Land Use Change

The land use change group included a set of **79 data records** classified as LUC looked at both agro-forestry or silvo-pasture (please refer to DL 4.1). The two categories were combined as no identifiable differences between the two land uses was found in the studies. The “Control” was either a cropland or grassland plot with no additional sources of OC from agriculture. The second batch of 10 LUC studies mostly looked at experiments where the paired plots were a combination of an arable (i.e. cropland) control versus a grassland treatment plot. To finish , LUC group was a smaller set of 22 experiments which looked at converting cropland or grassland to forestry (without any additional grazing or other sources of OC from agriculture in the Treatment plot).

2.2.3. Climate data

Data for monthly average air temperature, rainfall, and potential evaporation were sourced from ERA5 (global reanalysis product) for an extent covering the LUCAS data from 1940 to 2022. These data were also used for the LTE simulations. The data were sourced from: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

2.2.4. Site/soil data

Two different types of data were collected: from long-term experiments (LTEs) and LUCAS. The LTE data were extracted from literature. We followed the process which had been carried out in Microsoft

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Excel within R (script LTE_data.Rmd) to create an data input file e.g. LTE.csv. Further data cleaning and subsetting was undertaken within the R environment.

The C stock values from the different LTE studies were undertaken and reported for different soil depths. This lack of uniformity within the LTE dataset causes difficulty when making comparisons between studies, especially for those with contrasting measures (treatments). Previous work by (Smith et al., 2000) applied a quadratic density function for this problem. Further development by (Abdalla et al., 2018) derived a scaling cumulative distribution function (c.d.f.) for soil density as a function of soil depth up to 1m. This enabled values at a given depth d (m) to be scaled to the equivalent values at a depth of interest (0.30 m in the case of Abdalla et al.). On account of our interest in the LUCAS data we modified the approach by (Abdalla et al., 2018) to scale the SOC stock data to a depth of 0.2 m using the following equations:

$$CF = \left(\left(22.1 - \frac{33.3d^2}{2} - \frac{14.8d^3}{3} \right) / 10.41667 \right) \quad (1)$$

$$SF = \left(\left(22.1 - \frac{33.3m^2}{2} - \frac{14.8m^3}{3} \right) / 10.41667 \right) / CF \quad (2)$$

$$SOC_{20} = SF \times SOC_m \quad (3)$$

where CF = correction factor, d = depth of interest which we set to 0.2 m, m = measurement depth when not 0.2 m, depth SF = scaling factor, SOC_{20} = Soil Organic Carbon Stock to 0.2m, SOC_m = Soil Organic Carbon Stock to the specific measured depth in each study.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Summary statistics were calculated for the key variables of interest: SOC stocks, emission factors and the simulated plant C inputs. The treatment factors were analysed with a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in an unbalanced design. The factorial model included the treatment factors which related to land use or management. ANOVA was only possible to be undertaken where there were sufficient observations were available. Consequently, this was at the following levels: Europe (all data) and for two countries (Germany and United Kingdom). In addition, ANOVA was undertaken for the Cambisol soil order. All statistical analysis was carried out using R software (R Core Team, 2023).

3. Estimation of Emission Factors and Stock Difference

3.1 Emission Factors

The IPCC Guidelines define the emission factor as: “the average emission rate of a given GHG (Green House Gas) for a given source, relative to units of activity” (IPCC, 2019). Different considerations are required regarding the tier level (i.e. Tier 1 vs. Tier 2). The calculated emission factors are specific according to the soil type, climate, and other factors such as location. The specific nature of emission factors means that they cannot be applied to other locations. As a result, the calculation of emission factors has been undertaken at a individual country level. The equation given below describes the emission factors:

$$EF = \frac{SOC_{treatment}}{SOC_{control}} \quad (4)$$

Where:

EF = emission factor

$SOC_{treatment}$ = SOC final stock of the treatment, tonnes C ha⁻¹

$SOC_{control}$ = SOC final stock of the control, tonnes C ha⁻¹

3.2. Stock Difference Method

The Stock-Difference Method was applied to estimate SOC stock change being the difference between SOC treatment and control:

$$C = \frac{(C_t - C_c)}{(t_2 - t_1)} \quad (5)$$

Where:

ΔC = annual carbon stock change, tonnes C yr⁻¹

C_c = carbon stock control t_1 , tonnes C

C_t = carbon stock treatment t_2 , tonnes C

$(t_2 - t_1)$ duration of study, yr⁻¹

A cautionary note is given by the 2019 Refinement of the IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2019) to ensure that there is no confounding on account of any area changes. Thus, the land use must remain the same remain the same for t_1 and t_2 . Here we used this method to estimate SOC changes for LTE's of WP4 data base.

4. Modelling to simulate plant carbon inputs

The model used for the WP4 soil organic carbon simulations was RothC (Coleman & Jenkinson, 2014). Preliminary simulations of the inverse modelling approach were run using the Windows version of RothC (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996). These results provided an initial indication of the estimated monthly plant inputs, however this was very time consuming as each study site was run separately and it was not possible to perform a uniform simulation with the same parameters for all LTE or LUCAS sites. Further description is given below on the modelling methodology which was implemented on the LTE and LUCAS datasets.

4.1. Model assumptions

The simulation modelling work was undertaken based on a number of assumptions. Implicitly there was established a direct relationship between the change in the soil C stocks and the simulated value of plant C inputs. (Stewart et al., 2007) discussed a linear relationship between soil C stocks and C inputs where there is steady-state saturation. For simplicity we assumed that there is no annual change in the plant C inputs. The simulation results were calculated to only produce positive plant C inputs. We undertook a series of back calculations to ensure that any potential negative plant C inputs would be equal to zero.

The classical inverse method to apply RothC is based upon a spin-up with a SOC stock value for the starting year of a given period (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996, Coleman et al., 1997). For the vast majority of LTE studies there was no SOC stock value available for the starting year. Nemo et al. (2017) showed that the spin-up parameterisation can significantly affect the final simulation results such as the plant C inputs. Therefore, as a result for the LTE studies we typically used the end (final) SOC stock value for the control treatment for the LTE data. For those studies where there was both starting and end SOC stocks available we undertook a comparison of the simulated plant C inputs. Using the end SOC stock values produced an underestimate in the plant C inputs compared to using the starting SOC stock.

4.2. Workflow description

This modelling work was produced using R version 4.1.1. The R software was run using RStudio 2023.06.1 Build 524 (R Core Team, 2023). An R project was created which provides the architecture for R markdown scripts used in this work (Figure. 2). The *here* package is used to navigate this for input-output operations. Open the R project (.Rproj) file first and then files from the “scripts” folder within the project (folder architecture in Table 1).

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Table 1: The folder architecture of modelling RothC with R software

Folder	Contents/Comment
Data	Sourced/raw data.
Output	Files saved from R.
Plots	Graphs, maps, figures.
RothC_run	Contains .exe files (> EXE_files). Directories are made here during workflow, copying in files to run the model.
Scripts	R scripts and R markdown files
setup_files	Contains three folders: C_input_files landman_scenarios user_setup_cols

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Figure 2. RothC modelling framework for estimating SOC stocks and changes under grassland.

The workflow allowed the model to be run in several ways:

- A) Calculate plant carbon inputs to spin-up the model to a given stock (using average weather and land management).
- B) Spin up to an equilibrium based on average weather and a given carbon input (this could be the calculated inputs from (A)).

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C) Spin up to equilibrium as in (B) then calculate the plant carbon inputs to achieve a given stock in a given time period (specified years) and specifying land management for the scenario period (using the same average whether as spin-up).

D) Spin up to equilibrium as in (B) then run beyond this for a given time period (specified years) and specifying land management for the scenario period (which could use input from (C) and yearly weather data).

A set of three sequential run_modes have been coded which:

1) acts like (A) above.

2) calculates the additional plant carbon input required to achieve year_end (or target) stock (acts like (C) above).

3) runs the model with the calculated inputs from (1) and (2) but uses the yearly weather for each site after spin-up (acts like (D) above).

Mode (2) allows for year_end or target stock to be lower than spin-up but large declines in a given timeframe cannot be modelled if they would require less than 0 t C/ha/year.

Modes (1) and (2) run the model twice: once to calculate the input (calc_inp) followed by running with the calculated inputs (simulation) so the resultant C stock at that stage can be compared. (these provide different directory and filenames e.g. "run_mode1_calc_inp", "run_mode1_simulation").

Where user attention is required for routine running this is sign posted in the chunk title and commented before the lines of code ("USER ATTENTION"). There were three main user attention areas: user setup files (2.1.1), model variables (2.1.2), and land management (2.1.3).

Calculation of plant C inputs

For each workflow approach there were steps included for the calculation of simulated plant C inputs. Plant C inputs were calculated such that modelled SOC stocks matched to the measured SOC stock at spin-up (run mode 1) and final stock (run mode 2). For run mode 1, an annual plant input of 1 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ was used and then scaled according to the resultant SOC stock and for run mode 2 an additional 1 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ was added to the calculated C input from run_mode 1 to then scale. This allowed for decreases in inputs where there were declines in SOC stock however if this would result in a negative plant input it was set to zero and we assume that the decline might fall out of scope of RothC or our applied scenario (e.g. an erosion event or changed management). This also assumes that declines were only due to C input which is an area that could be addressed in future.

4.3. User setup files

The file to assign to the sites variable, ideally a csv file containing at least the variables listed below for user_input_vars (e.g. sites <- read.csv (here("data","output","Dataset_name_rothc.csv")).

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The name of the exe file to use (without.exe) (e.g. RothC_exe <- "RothC_Code-1.0.0"). The file to assign to user_setup_vars, containing names in the sites file for required variables (e.g.

```
user_setup_vars <- read.csv(here("setup_files","user_setup_cols","LTE_user_setup.csv"),
                           header = FALSE))
```

Example of data required in the user setup .csv file here:

run_name	LTE	
ID_col	loc_prof	
long_col	longitude_dec	
lat_col	latitude_dec	
clay_col	clay	
depth_col	max_sample_depth	
ref_cstock_col	adj_ctrl_stock	
year_start_col	Year_start	
year_end_col	Year_end	
C_input_col		

This file should have entries as above but replacing the second component of each line with the corresponding names for: a run name for folder directories and naming output files (e.g. dataset name) followed by corresponding column names from the sites data frame a user supplies for: an ID column, longitude, latitude, clay (%), depth (cm), C stock (t ha^{-1}) for calculating the IOM pool, year to start the modelling (e.g. which year to spin up to), and a year to end the modelling (which is not necessarily used e.g. when estimating plant inputs or just running to an equilibrium C stock). Following this in the code, each element is assigned to a variable that is used later in the code. This saves a user changing the code explicitly for each of these variables or having to harmonise data to a particular naming convention.

Note that above the C_input_col entry is blank. Since the code will look for these by the text of the first component, a blank entry will not disrupt the code, however, this is only really applicable for this variable as it is only required for a particular mode variable (**C_input is 1** in the next section).

There can be multiple data input files; for LTE or LUCAS data. For the LTE sites this could be separated into files which includes the C stock for the starting year, while another data file includes ONLY the final C stock values.

4.4. Model variables

Switches for each mode are the variables **est_plant**, **eqm**, and **C_input**. The first is whether to estimate yearly plant C input, the next is to stop at equilibrium or continue on, and the last is how to provide C input information (if not superseded by **est_plant**).

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If **est_plant is 1** is used, then the model is run to equilibrium (sets **eqm** to 1) with 1 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ plant input and the chosen land management scenario(s) (explained below). The resultant stock is used to back-calculate the required rate of plant C input. The run to equilibrium using 1 t plant C/ ha with the “Year start”.

If **est_plant is 2**, then the **eqm** and **C_input** variables will become relevant.

First, we’ll cover **eqm**:

So, if **est_plant is 2** and **eqm is 1**, then the model runs to equilibrium.

If **est_plant is 2** and **eqm is 2** (or anything else) then the model will spin up to equilibrium (using average weather) up to and including “Year_start” and continue yearly until and including “Year_end”.

For **C_input**, there are three values this can take:

If **C_input is 1**, then a column in the site data (**C_input_col**) will provide the annual C input (t C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹) to apply to each site for the whole duration of the run.

If **C_input is 2**, then a separate data frame will need to be supplied which has *ID*, *year*, and *C_input* to provide the annual C input for each year. This needs to be from year_start to year_end.

This describes how to control the modes in the workflow. If a Year_start is outside of the climate or NPP date ranges then the code will stop and a message will be raised during the input_file creation chunk stating this and the range of years. If Year_end exceeds the data, no error will appear but the input files will stop at the limit of the climate or NPP data.

4.5. Land management

Land management in RothC is represented by four columns with 12 entries (months) for plant C input, FYM C input, plant cover, and DPM/RPM ratio (relating to quality of incoming plant material).

Within the workflow, a separate script is called (landman_template_list.R) which contains a list of land management scenarios. These are to be user specified, and the list can accommodate as many entries as required for the sites. Each entry represents a year from January to December with 12 values (one per month). The components of a land management scenario are as follows:

Plant C input is represented as a distribution of carbon (as a monthly decimal fraction summing to 1 across the year) from plants (growing/roots/residue). This is then multiplied by a value in the workflow depending on the “C_input” variable.

FYM C input is the monthly t C ha⁻¹ from farmyard manure (this is currently the organic amendment with parameters in the RothC executable, but this could be changed in the code which has been released on GitHub). In this case the actual values to use should be supplied and these are the corresponding amounts of carbon in the FYM not the FYM fresh or dry matter rates (for detail see DL 4.1).

The plant cover entries should be 1 or 0 (not a decimal fraction) which relates to plant cover being present during that month or not, respectively, (e.g. judgement might be made as to how soon after

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sowing a crop it provides protection if the soil is bare after harvest). For example, for arable (winter crop) the cover was assumed to be bare in September and October.

DPM/RPM ratio portions incoming plant material between these pools. For arable and improved grassland this is generally set to 1.44. For agroforestry and woodland/ forest sites the DPM/RPM values were 0.67 and 0.25 respectively.

The list of data frames can be added to by copying the `data.frame()` code to create an additional list element and editing to fit the desired land management. List index (1+) is used to select the land management required for a site, so names are just descriptive for your own benefit.

A land management scenario is required for each site (within a single csv) containing *ID*, *year*, and *landman_code*, where *ID* is the site ID repeated row-wise for the number of steps in the scenario, *year* starts at *year_start* followed by years where the land management changes, and *landman_code* is the list index associated with that site and year combination e.g.

ID	year	Landman_code
Site_1	1985	1
Site_1	1990	2
Site_1	1997	3
Site_1	2000	4
Site_2	1985	1
Site_2	1997	3
Site_2	2000	5

For Site_1, in the above, the workflow will use the land management at list index 1 (from the `landman_template_list.R` script) from 1985 to 1989, then from 1990-1996 it will use list index 2, then from 1997-1999 it will use list index 3, and from 2000 until year end (specified in site data) it will use list index 4. Site_2 will be run similarly for its specified year and list index combinations.

This might require manual data entry into a csv file, depending on how specific or general the scenarios need to be across sites.

A dummy file has been provided for the LTE data, along with the code to generate this in the workflow script.

5.5. RothC code/exe file

The RothC model was downloaded from the zenodo release (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10707407) (Coleman et al., 2024), and the `RothC.for` and `Shell.for` files were compiled in Microsoft Visual Studio 2019 to create an exe file for use in the workflow. The RothC model was written in Fortran and was run from R studio. Further details on the RothC 26.3 model are available (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996).

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